

The Government Expenditures Impact on Namibia's Economic Growth

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Economic growth is important for poverty reduction, income inequality reduction, and enhancing a country's standard of living, among other things. Using time-series data of Namibia's economy from 1991 to 2019, we use the vector auto-regression model to examine the impact of general government expenditures on Namibia's economic growth. This study shows a long-run relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Namibia. However, government expenditures have a weak influence on Gross Domestic Product. Moreover, there is a statistically significant positive error correction model coefficient, which implies that increasing government spending drives economic growth in the long run. The results of the generalized supremum augmented Dickey-Fuller show that the Gross Domestic Product has explosive tendencies. Thus, the findings suggest Namibia's government adopt an expansionary fiscal policy to boost economic growth. Therefore, shifting government resources to a more productive sector may result in economic growth.

Keywords: ECONOMIC GROWTH, PUBLIC EXPENDITURE, RIGHT-TAIL AUGMENTED DICKEY-FULLER, ERROR CORRECTION MODEL

Introduction

Government expenditure is an important determinant of economic growth. Hence government policies that try to spend money more efficiently on productive sectors lead to economic growth. Governments are responsible for redistributing scarce resources through the production of goods, the purchase of commodities, and the provision of services (Ortiz-Ospina and Roser 2016). Moreover, government expenditures are required to improve a country's population's knowledge, skills, and education. Investing in human capital benefits the government because it increases labour force productivity, which leads to GDP growth (Shafuda and De 2020). Previous academics have investigated the relationship between government expenditures and economic growth, but the results are mixed. Authors such as Shafuda and De (2020), Nhangwini and Tleane, (2019), Leshoro, (2017), and Chen et al. (2020) employ a Keynesian hypothesis to examine the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. According to

Keynesian theory, government expenditure plays a significant role in boosting economic growth. In the long run, if public expenditures spent well, they can assist drive economic growth; this is because increased government spending increases GDP growth (Leshoro 2017,). Economic shocks, on the other hand, can cause time-series data to bubble up.

Some economists question whether government expenditure can improve the economy or not. Their views are from the scarcity of empirical evidence demonstrating the favorable effects of increased government expenditure on economic growth in developing nations (Nhlangwini and Tleane, 2019). The issues with government expenditure have the potential to suffocate the private sector activity in an economy. Another problem of government expenditure is encounter by the smaller government when the country is increasing spending on unproductive sectors, and these slow down economic growth. On the other hand, Africa's government can raise government expenditure to improve economic growth, market failures, and economic recessions (Ariotti, 2020; Donghyun Park, 2015; Wen and Wang, 2013). These make economic growth essential for various reasons, including poverty reduction, income inequality reduction, and raising a country's standard of living.

Nhlangwini & Tleane (2019) examine the relationship between government expenditures and economic growth in South Africa using Johansen cointegration analysis and the Vector Error Correction Model on time series from 1997 to 2017. The author's findings support the Keynesian notion that government spending boosts long-run economic growth in South Africa. The same methodology was used in research conducted in Namibia, and the results confirmed Keynes' claim (Shafuda & De, 2020). It is argued by Shafuda & De (2020) that increasing government expenditure on investment in creative companies can lead to a meaningful growth of the Namibian economy. Suanin (2015) investigates the relationship between differential government expenditure and economic growth in Thailand using VECM on data from 1993 to 2001. The author demonstrates a long-run relationship between government expenditures and economic growth. Suanin (2015) suggest the government should play a critical role in enhancing the technological capabilities of enterprises to increase productivity across the country and support long-run economic growth.

Another study using VECM in Vanuatu shows mixed results on the influence of government spending on economic growth from perspective of financing. If government spending is financed by tax money, it has a negative effect on economic growth. Another conclusion indicates that government spending positively influences economic growth when it is financed by non-tax revenue. The research reveals that ECT outcomes are negative and significant, indicating a convergence process in the Vanuatu economic system (Chen et al., 2020). Any change in the system it can return to equilibrium. A previous study examines the relationship between government consumption expenditures and economic growth in 34 OECD countries using panel data from 1995 to 2011. The study shows that government consumption expenditures had no evident impact on

economic growth (Connolly & Li, 2016). The previous literature indicates that the impact of government spending on economic growth results is still inconsistent.

In recent years Namibia's public expenditure composition has been a source of concern. The Namibian government has difficulty meeting a 20:80 country target ratio of development to operational expenditure. Development expenditure is critical for boosting economic growth (Intelliconn, 2019). Namibia's unsustainable spending accounts prompt the government to cut spending by N\$1bn in fiscal 2018/19 and adopt fiscal consolidation to minimize government spending despite slow economic growth is (Menges, 2018). Furceri et al. (2018) argue against the adoption of fiscal consolidation leads to increased poverty and income inequality, which harms long-run growth in contrast to fiscal expansions, which lower inequality. Shafuda & De (2020) suggest that implementing a goal-driven expansionary spending program may increase Namibia's economic growth in the long run. According to this research view on the choice of government, spending program is important for the Namibian government public finance sustainability.

In this study, the Johansen test investigates the long-run relationship among variables employing the VECM since variables are stationary at first difference. The results of the generalized supremum augmented Dickey-Fuller show that the Gross Domestic Product has explosive behaviour. This study shows a long-run relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Namibia. However, government expenditures may have a weak influence on Gross Domestic Product as indicated by variance decomposition. We examine the speed of adjustment within GDP with the change in public spending whereby findings show a statistically significant positive error correction model coefficient, which may imply that increasing government spending drives economic growth in the long run.

Materials and methods

This study examines the impacts of public expenditure on Namibia's economic growth using two variables. The study's dependent variable is economic growth (GDP), whereas the independent variable is government expenditure (EXPEG). The real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) measures economic growth (gross domestic product). The time series data are from the Namibia Statistics Agency and span the years 1991 to 2019. The time-series data are in constant 2010 Namibia million-dollar prices. The ADF Test, generalized supremum ADF (GSADF) tests, supremum ADF (SADF), Johansen cointegration, Vector Error Correction Model, and diagnostic tests have all been used. Our general model specification is based on the model of (Nhlanguini & Tleane, 2019). The model is as follows:

$$\ln GDP = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln EXPEG + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Explosive behaviour testing

This article applies right-tail Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) to time series data to discover explosive behaviour. Phillips, Wu, and Yu (2011) standard and supremum ADF (SADF), as well as Phillips, Shi, and Yu (2015) GSADF, are used in this investigation. The right-tail augmented Dickey-Fuller test is more accurate than standard tests in detecting one or more explosive behaviours (Phillips, Wu, and Yu, 2011; Phillips, Shi, and Yu, 2015). Fiscal regulators can use the recursive right-sided unit root test to provide sound warning signals for policy action and market monitoring utilizing real-time data. Compared to the standard ADF, which uses the complete sample, the right-tail augmented Dickey-Fuller algorithm uses the regression window size. The bubble test is designed to determine whether there is a unit root and whether explosive behaviours exist. The bubble test is based on the null hypothesis of the existence of a unit root and the alternative hypothesis of the presence of explosive behaviours. The absence of explosive behaviours is established empirically by rejecting the null hypothesis. These statistical tests are Monte Carlo simulations that assume Gaussian innovations and produce a graphical depiction of the date stamping technique (Caspi, 2017).

Table 1 shows the critical values determined using Monte Carlo simulations with 1000 replications and a window size of 10. GDP has an explosive behaviour, whereas EXPEG has a unit root. According to Figure 1, the GDP series experienced explosive growth between 2004 and 2005, during which domestic investment in Namibia's tertiary sectors fell. As a result, exports of minerals, beef, and fish were decreased, all of which had a negative impact on production. However, some Namibian minerals, including copper, uranium, nickel, diamonds, and platinum, hit record highs during the same year, considerably contributing to Namibia's growth.

Table 1.ADF, SADF and GSADF tests results

Variables	ADF		SADF		GSADF	
	Statistics	P-value	Statistics	P-values	Statistics	P-values
GDP	-1.842583	0.3360	0.577119	0.0310**	1.507568	0.0160**
EXPEG	-1.671219	0.2370	0.350440	0.0570	0.350440	0.0570

Notes: ***, **, and * respectively significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

Figure1: Date-stamping bubble periods in GDP
GSADF test

Source: Based on E-views results

Unit roots analysis

The ADF test and Phillips-Peron were used to evaluate GEXPE and GDP for the presence of unit root. As given in Table 2, the data show that both variables are integrated at order one, rejecting the null hypothesis of the unit root at first difference.

Table 2: Unit roots test

Variables	Test	statistic at intercept	Critical value at 5%	Probability	Results
GDP	ADF	-3.072	-2.976	0.0409	I(1)
	PP	-3.126	-2.976	0.0364	I(1)
EXPEG	ADF	-3.9383	-3.588	0.0241	I(1)
	PP	-3.960	-3.588	0.0234	I(1)

Source: Based on E-views results

Cointegration test results

In this study, the Johansen test was employed to determine long-term connections between variables. Based on the Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue tests results, Tables 3 and 4 reveal that there is cointegration. Therefore, the null hypothesis that cointegration does not exist is rejected. These findings show that variables move together in the long run, have an equilibrium relationship, and are linked linearly. The findings support the suggestion of Shafuda & De (2020) that the Namibia government must choose an

expansionary expenditure strategy in order to accelerate economic growth.

Table 3: Trace Test

Hypothesized cointegration	No of	Trace Statistics	0.05 Critical value	Prob
None		13.746	15.494	0.0902
At most 1		0.557	3.841	0.4556

Table 4: Max- Eigen Test

Hypothesized cointegration	No of	Max- Eigen Statistics	0.05 Critical value	Prob
None		13.190	14.265	0.073
At most 1		0.557	3.841	0.4556

Source: Based on E-views results

Table 5's Normalized Test shows that government spending is positive and has a long-run effect on GDP. When government i increase spending, so as will be an increase in GDP.

Table 5: Normalized coefficient Test

LGDP	LEXPEG
1.000	-1.070
	(0.046)

Source: Based on E-views results

The vector error correction model (VECM)

Using Maximum Likelihood estimation and Least Square, VECM analysis detects short-run and long-run effects on the connection between non-stationary variables. Where the VAR model has a shortcoming, VECM overcomes it. The generic model of VECM deducts a lag of the endogenous variable ((Hapsari et al. 2020). Because the optimum lag of the Akaike information criteria was 1, this study utilizes 0 lag in VECM. Table 6 shows the ECM results, which reveal that the GDP coefficient is the dependent variable and that government expenditure is significantly positive. This ECM study's conclusions are congruent with those of Suanin (2015), demonstrating that a rise in government spending leads to an increase in GDP in the long run. These findings may suggest that there is no long-term causal link between government expenditures and economic growth. The paper then uses right-tail Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Variance Decomposition to identify explosive behaviours in time series in table 1. The speed of adjustment indicates how quickly the model returns to equilibrium after a disturbance in the system.

Table 6: Error Correction Term results to economic growth.

Error correction error	Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	T-statistics
	D(LGDP)	0.190	0.077	2.459
ECT				

	D(LEXPEG)	0.337	0.105	4.214
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Source: Based on E-views results

The estimation of the model of VECM is as follows:

$$D(LGDP) = C(1) * (LGDP(-1) - 1.09502762293 * LEXPEG(-1) - 0.360132292297) + C(2)$$

Table 7 illustrates that in the long run, GDP has a strong influence on itself. In contrast, government spending has a weak influence on GDP. Our findings are comparable to those of (Shafuda & De, 2020) of there is no strong long-run link between government spending and economic growth.

Table 7: Variance Decomposition test

VD GDP PERIOD	S.E	DGDP	DEXPEG
1	2563.015	100.0000	0.000000
2	2838.558	89.44750	10.55250
3	3108.863	82.91090	17.08910
4	3147.757	81.16533	18.83467
5	3153.630	80.90608	19.09392

Source: Based on E-views results

Stability test

The diagnostic tests on the VECM model indicate that the residuals are normally distributed, there is no heteroskedasticity or autocorrelation in the residuals and the model is suitable for modeling Namibian variables.

Conclusion

This study examines the effect of government expenditure on economic growth. Stationarity analysis, cointegration using the Johannes test, and VECM were the econometrics tests performed. The findings of this research show that the two variables are integrated at order one. The Johannes test results show that government spending and economic growth are cointegrated. The findings of VECM confirm the existence of a long-run relationship between government spending and economic growth in Namibia. Another finding of this article is a significant positive ECM coefficient, implying that increased government spending leads to increased economic growth over time, consistent with the Keynesian hypothesis. Furthermore, the study estimates the variance decomposition to determine the extent to which external shocks account for the variance in GDP forecast error variance. GDP shocks have a long-run effect on GDP, but government shocks have little effect on GDP. In the long run, government spending impacts Namibian economic activity and

resources may be reallocated to productive sectors to encourage economic growth. Increased government spending broadens the fiscal base, lowering income disparities and poverty. The test indicates a statistically significant positive link between government expenditures and economic growth, which has substantial economic consequences. The diagnostic tests determined that the model is neither serially correlated, or heteroskedasticity and that the residuals are normally distributed. This study is limited to general government spending figures in Namibia, not specific sectors of government spending.

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